

Navigating TechCentral's Industrial Design Ecosystem

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663
Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and
Initiating Change, 2021 cohort

Chenuli Abeywardena, William Andrew, Nethra Deepak, Jianwei Ji, Alexander
Neethling, and Annabelle Sghabi

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Team

Chenuli Abeywardena, William Andrew, Nethra Deepak, Jianwei Ji, Alexander Neethling, and Annabelle Sghabi

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Subject Coordination

Assoc. Prof Martin Bliemel

Course Director (Diploma in Innovation)

Director, Research

UTS: TD School

Yara Vasina

Tutor, 94663 Navigating Ecosystems

UTS: TD School

Foreword

This report is part of a series of student-generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework, conducted in collaboration with multiple industry partners and interviews with stakeholders in the ecosystem. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws directly on Martin's prior experience in visualising entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals that will bring the ecosystem forward.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

Methodology

The cohort of 50+ students was divided into random teams, each of which could choose their own ecosystem to focus on, with the only caveat being that it relates to TechCentral. Generally, the ecosystems were geographically in the immediate vicinity of TechCentral³, but varied significantly in terms of their sectoral focus.

Each team was instructed to consider the types of stakeholder based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,⁴ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE). Teams adopt a qualitative approach, involving interviewing a broad range of participants to extract insights on their interpersonal connections and interrelations between factors and to identify specific opportunities for change. Each participant is believed to have a clear view of their immediate ecosystem, from which teams stitch together the more holistic view of how the ecosystem works.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.uts.edu.au/news/innovation/welcome-neighbourhood-tech-central>

⁴ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

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1 History of the Industrial Design Ecosystem

The objective history of the industrial design sector (IDS) around Surry Hills includes the evolution of over 180 years in human creativity and design. This interaction between industrial designers and natural resources in implementing aesthetic appeal and functionality in their products has contributed to Australian culture and helped lay the foundation of the ecosystem (van Dam et al., 2020). Such interplay between intellect and intuition saw the industrial design sector improve the quality of the manufacturing industry and of other established resources and sectors, as seen in the time map below. As well as providing quality, the industrial design sector has also provided entrepreneurial growth and innovation that continues stronger today. Such innovation has seen the industrial design sector generate designers from a milieu of disciplines such as technology, science, architecture and engineering. The people of Sydney, incubators, accelerators, firms, education institutions and policy makers in the Australian government helped develop the ecosystem that has untapped capabilities for the future. Despite setbacks, Tech Central can strengthen the industrial design sector and has the potential to innovate beyond the ecosystem as a part of Tech Central but also as a competitive ecosystem on the world stage.

The Industrial Design Sector (IDS) around Surry Hills can be traced to education institutions like the Sydney Mechanics' School of Arts along with the college of Technical Advancement and Further Learning. The Sydney Mechanics' School of Arts was formed in 1833 in a meeting of 200 people with a progressivist mindset based on the first Industrial Revolution and the cultural milieu of the period (SMSA, 2021). The Sydney Mechanics' School of Arts with the college of Technical Advancement and Further learning spearheaded in the region around Surry Hills education for men and women, particularly in areas such as skilled tradesmen like blacksmiths, bricklayers, carpenters, and stonemasons of industry.

The Sydney Mechanics' School of Arts served as a model of education in developing the industrial design sector for several other institutions such as the University of Technology, Sydney in 1870 and the University of New South Wales in 1949 (ABC, 2016). In 1958, the Design Council of Australia was created with the collaboration of designers, industrialists, and policy makers in the Commonwealth Government in promoting Australia's economic recovery (Good Design Australia, 2021).

In 1992, the Powerhouse Museum in Ultimo collaborated with the Australian Design Awards program and implemented the Powerhouse Museum Design Award and Selection. Outstanding products that showed innovation in materials, design, or technology which improved the quality of living in Australians, were displayed in the Powerhouse Museum.

In 1995, the National Design Review Steering Committee represented by the University of Technology Sydney, the Australian Academy of Design, Baulderstone Hornibrook, Bilcon Engineering, Sebel Furniture, Design Field, Royal Institute of Architects, Hambro Grantham Limited, Curtin University of Technology, Design Institute of Australia, Department of Industry, Science and Technology, AusIndustry, Australian Quality Council, the Australian quality council and others submitted the National Design Review Report: Competing By Design to the Commonwealth Government. The report emphasised the value of Design with Australian innovation, economic safety and social qualities. Also, the Design products were acknowledged and celebrated through a design awards program. The following years saw the Industrial Design Sector neglected. The IDS experienced a rise in operating costs that crippled the quality and quantity in design products which also affected the Australian Design Awards. The Australian Design Awards joins the global body for Industrial Design, the International Council of Societies of Industrial Design.

In 2000, the Industrial Design Sector recovered financially through the success of designs submitted to the Australian Design Awards. The Australian design award, not-for-profit also gained a high reputation within Australia; gaining the support from mainstream media outlets such as the ABC and Business Review Weekly magazine.

In 2001, the Prime Minister of Australia, The Hon. John Howard wrote a Foreword for the Australian Design Awards Yearbook. Howard expressed the qualities of creativity and innovation of industrial design in economic and social prosperity in the 21st century.

In 2008, the Australian Design Awards on their 50th anniversary was renamed the Australian International Design Awards and international products in industrial design entered the Awards. The following saw entries from 16 countries with Australian designer Marc Newson, winning the award for that year.

2015, the Australian Good Design Awards accept products from a variety of Industrial design disciplines such as Product Design, Service Design, Digital Design, Architectural Design, and Social Innovation and Business Model Design.

2017 saw Good Design Australia collaborated with Channel TEN and ONE in a tv series called Australia by Design. Australia by Design uncovers stories that resulted in innovation that have improved the quality of living in areas such as technology, transport, and medicine. This was to appeal to a more contemporary audience to inform a wider demographic of design.

In 2018, Good Design Australia and Australian Good Design Awards celebrated 60 years in promoting innovation in industrial design. The Industrial design sector diversifies further by implementing and celebrating Engineering Design, Fashion Design and the Indigenous Designer Award and others.

In 2019, Inventia Rastrum 3D Bioprinter took the Good Design Award for innovation in using 3D printing technology to bio print living cells and the potential to innovate biology and medical research. The inaugural 'Women in Design Award' is launched to celebrate women participating in the innovation and industrial design sector.

In 2020, despite the COVID-19 pandemic, the Good design awards continued to go ahead through online submissions with the Nurochek System winning the Good Design Award designed in partnership with 4Design and Headspace. The Nurochek System is the first unique device of its kind, assessing neurological health in people at risk from diseases such as dementia.

2 Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map

Figure 1: EE Map

2.1 The theory behind the EE map

The unique shape of the Ecosystem Map represents that of the renowned industrial design progress map, which is a tool used by designers to track their progress throughout their different projects from a tertiary student level up to a professional consultancy level.

As this design is familiar within the industrial design ecosystem, it was only fitting to take inspiration from the progress tracker to aid in explaining the ecosystem as a whole as the ecosystem is also a constant work in progress. (Design Council UK, 2021) The idea behind adopting this design principle into the ee map was to symbolise the “up and down” progress of the industrial design ecosystem and how this affects the various stakeholders through the ‘discovery’ and ‘development’ of different connections. This, similarly is how designers make sense of their projects, through discovery through to development and delivery.

2.2 The design of the shape

Each side of the ecosystem is even; the diamond shapes are evenly distributed so equal hierarchy throughout the map is conveyed for the stakeholders. The various colours used for the 'stakeholder circles' are an illustration of how the map has been divided, making visually clear links between stakeholders of similar areas within the sector; e.g. policy makers and education.

The light grey colour is used from the left hand side through to the right hand side to create a sense of continuity and a visual path to follow through the EE map. The two initial smaller grey circles represent the past of the ecosystem, although there is no written detail to explain this on the map, the visual aid of the circles placed before the diamond symbolsises the sector's history. The two light grey circles at the end of the map next to the larger circle labeled 'Tech Central' symbolise the future of the entrepreneurial ecosystem and allows an easy transition for new stakeholders to be a part of the map. As the geographical location of Tech Central is on the doorstep of the Surry Hills precinct, the NSW Government run startup hub is predicted to house stakeholders of the industrial design ecosystem in the near future, foreshadowing the hub to be a significant stakeholder within the ecosystem in the future. The lighter grey square outline provides a clear straight guide across the map, distinguishing the interconnections and the framework for the entrepreneurial industrial design ecosystem to flourish.

2.2.1 Stakeholder connections within the map

The stakeholders are represented by colour coded circles on the outside of the diamond shape with the variations of colours separately identifying the stakeholders into categories

2.2.2 Stakeholder interactions for the map

To identify the significant stakeholders within the ecosystem for the map we conducted secondary research and two primary interviews to gain industry insight into how the ecosystem is to run and how the connections formed. Through our interview with Michael Hoppe he explained the importance of having an industrial designer on board a business team to create more credibility to the company's designs and products (Hop Design, 2021). Through this discovery of the industrial design sector's involvement with many other sectors this influenced how we constructed the EE map to represent the equal hierarchy of the ecosystem as each stakeholder is significant in allowing the overall ecosystem to work collaboratively.

3 Leverage Proposal

3.1 Big Why?

Our group's aim in the growth of the (IDS) focuses in three areas which seeks much needed innovation and entrepreneurship for a competitive ecosystem. Firstly, we recommend the IDS around Surry Hills and subsequently Tech Central in generating more social resources (Spigel & Harrison, 2017). Secondly, help promote ecodesign by innovating new production processes (Ruadesign, n.d.). Thirdly, the IDS can lend their innovation to space entrepreneurship as many economies plan to colonise the moon (Dovey, 2019). Thereby, with the arrival of Tech Central, a unified IDS is needed for entrepreneurship and innovation

3.2 What?

Through analysis of the Entrepreneurial ecosystem and responses from interviews, we believe there are a range of opportunities present. The first of these opportunities is the possibility of expanding the anchor tenants of Tech Central to better represent the diverse nature of Sydney's technological ecosystem. Including tenants for Industrial design will provide a collective sense of community the industrial design sector is sorely missing. In a similar vein, the lack of community and collaboration within the industrial design ecosystem provides opportunities for a new form of collaborative award. Having industrial design awards specifically focused on industrial design partners working out of tech central would provide a motivating factor and sense of community for all those involved.

3.3 Who?

The Being Group is a company that is passionate about loving the people they work with and their environment, and having worked with multinational companies, government agencies, start-ups and not-for-profits, the company could contribute to the overall EE, including other sectors and organisations (The Being Group, 2021). The Being Group plays a very important role in the ecosystem. They provide strategic consulting services to different government agencies in different fields, from human services, public services to finance. They also provide strategic design and targeted solutions with companies and organizations in different industries. Cooperation with government and business will promote the interconnection of policy, technology, finance and environmental protection in the entire entrepreneurial ecosystem. Furthermore, by being a part of this Tech Central EE The Being Group can have increased 'access to funding and resources', as mentioned in the interview (interview reference, 2021). The company states that 'diversity is key' within such an ecosystem, and that space within the EE 'should be available to anyone who is interested' (interview reference, 2021).

Michael Hoppe is the founder of HOP design company. He is also a tutor at UTS and has a great positive impact on students. Michael Hoppe's products have won Good Design Awards, IDEA, IF and Red Dot Design Awards. Hoppe's recent startup of the 'YBELL fitness' has also won many of the prestigious design awards and places him directly within the entrepreneurial ecosystem. His design and the company have a close relationship with the design atmosphere and development in the ecosystem. At the same time, he is also one of the potential tenants of tech central. He will stimulate the industrial design awareness and cooperation opportunities of enterprises in the ecosystem. In the interview, Hoppe said that industrial design is an 'indispensable part of the ecosystem. Every industry needs product design.' He is committed to using design to give users a good user experience. They also have close cooperation relationships with many different industries. They are very welcome to cooperate with start-up companies to seek common development opportunities. When interviewing Michael, he stressed on the importance of funding and legal organisations, especially for start-ups within the IDS. Successful and authoritative designers have played a significant role in promoting the development of industrial design in the entire ecosystem.

3.4 How & When?

For change in the EE, concepts should be based pertaining to natural resource preservation, renewable source usage while avoiding rivalry with agricultural land, energy conservation, prohibition of hazardous components and so on. Establishing paths for long-lasting materials, mass and cost reductions, recycling, and actual reuse of recycled plastics that would save energy, resources, and contamination. Instilling the value of understanding how resources travel throughout the ecosystem and

how they are created including the recycling from both successful and failed endeavors. Strengthening connections between entrepreneurs and their surroundings, which includes dynamic local community, organizational, and cultural processes and players that support and facilitate business development. Analyzing the EE framework's applicability beyond high-tech regional contexts in industrialized countries, but also at the urban level.

3.5 Little Why

Our group has identified the Industrial design sector (IDS) as a fragmented ecosystem with current challenges including a lack of social resources and inadequate venture capital. The positive attributes of this proposal include a development of social resources. These can arrive by talented workers, risk capital and mentorship from skilled entrepreneurs who start and adjust business enterprises (Spigel & Harrison 2017). However, there are less than 4,000 industrial designers with most centralised outside Surry Hills, there can be a lack of entrepreneurs with understanding of the IDS (Job Outlook, 2016). A nominated stakeholder for this enterprise includes HOP Design and YBell fitness who can share their success in entrepreneurial development, utilising new technologies such as 3D printing and their vision in durable products (HOP Design, 2018). This can emulate a positive outcome to the IDS EE since mentorship programs and skilled labour are known to support growth within an ecosystem (Guerrero et al., 2020). This can emulate a positive outcome to the IDS EE since mentorship programs and skilled labour are known to support growth within an ecosystem (Guerrero et al., 2020).

Our vision for the IDS is to aid plans in preserving environmental sustainability. Since the second industrial revolution, the environment has been impacted by excessive waste, pollution and resource depletion. The remedy to maintain environmental sustainability is to implement circular production processes, design for circular consumption, design policies and education around a circular economy (van Dam et al., 2020). The circular economy is a constructive system where energy leakage, resource input, waste and emission are reduced by closing and narrowing material and energy loops. We nominated 4Design for their vision in developing technical products at a significantly lower cost to their clients (4Design, 2019) Thereby, potentially saving money in resources and possibly making the IDS resource independent. However, a negative outcome of a circular economy could lead to issues previously unseen in terms of product and process quality (Barros et al., 2021). Organizations may have to focus more on quality management practices (Barros et al., 2021).

Our final leverage proposal is to further develop the IDS in promoting space entrepreneurship in the coming decade. The coming decade will see economies such as Japan colonise and mine the moon which has billions of dollars in resources (Dovey, 2019). We have nominated The Being Group to have dense social networks with access to venture capitalists and the Commonwealth Government and valuable experience with multinational companies, government agencies, start-ups and not-for-profits. This would grant the IDS not only an opportunity to improve the quality of living of humans on the moon but to transform and design products that can withstand conditions of space. However, poor cultural perceptions, perceived technical risk and a lack of awareness may negatively impact the growth of space entrepreneurship within the IDS EE (Wang, 2014). Therefore, it is important that organisations like The Being Group emphasize policy maker support from the Commonwealth Government in order to promote space entrepreneurship.

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